

Schrödinger's Cat, Gravitational Waves, and the Information Leak Behind Decoherence – Pre Print V2

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Abstract

We propose that gravitational-wave distinguishability provides a universal, information-theoretic mechanism for decoherence in quantum superpositions involving massive systems. When alternative quantum histories imprint distinguishable gravitational radiation states into spacetime, which-branch information exists in principle even in the absence of measurement. This suppresses interference purely through unitary entanglement with the gravitational field. Unlike collapse models, this framework relies only on standard quantum mechanics and the information-carrying capacity of gravitational radiation. We argue heuristically that the Planck mass emerges as an information-theoretical crossover scale beyond which gravitationally induced decoherence becomes unavoidable. To clarify the conceptual content, we introduce a Schrödinger's-cat-type thought experiment in which one branch of a quantum superposition produces colliding black holes and gravitational waves, while the other does not. In this limit case, spacetime itself functions as an irreversible which-branch environment. The analysis positions gravity not as a modifier of quantum mechanics, but as a universal information channel contributing to the quantum-classical transition.

Keywords: Gravitational decoherence; gravitational waves; quantum–classical transition; information-theoretic decoherence; Planck mass; quantum superpositions; environmental entanglement; spacetime information; gravitational radiation; macroscopic quantum systems; quantum gravity.

1. Introduction

The emergence of classical behavior from quantum mechanics is now widely understood in terms of *decoherence*: the suppression of interference due to entanglement with environmental degrees of freedom, without any modification of unitary dynamics. In this framework, classicality arises not from collapse, but from the proliferation of which-branch information into uncontrolled environmental channels. This perspective was developed most clearly in the work of Zurek, who showed how environmental monitoring selects robust pointer states through environment-induced superselection (“einselection”) [1,2]. While decoherence has been studied extensively for electromagnetic and thermal environments, gravity is often assumed to be operationally negligible because of its weakness. However, gravity possesses radiative degrees of freedom. Gravitational waves carry information about the motion of mass–energy and propagate irreversibly into spacetime. This raises the question of whether spacetime itself can function as an information-bearing environment. Related ideas have been explored in several different contexts. Pikovski *et al.* showed that gravitational time dilation can act as a universal decohering mechanism for internal degrees of freedom [3]. Anastopoulos and Hu analyzed the notion of “gravitational cat states,” emphasizing how gravitational fields can become entangled with macroscopic superpositions [4]. Blencowe formulated an effective-field-theory treatment of gravitationally induced decoherence without

modifying quantum mechanics [5]. These works motivate the idea that gravity may contribute to the quantum–classical transition through purely unitary entanglement. In contrast, other approaches propose that gravity fundamentally alters quantum mechanics. Penrose argued that gravity triggers objective state reduction [6], and Diósi introduced a stochastic gravitational master equation that violates strict unitarity [7]. Reviews of such collapse-type models are given by Bassi *et al.* [8]. The present work does *not* adopt this perspective. We assume standard quantum mechanics throughout and treat the gravitational field as an ordinary quantum environment. Decoherence arises here not from new dynamics, but from information leakage into gravitational radiation. Finally, experimental progress toward macroscopic quantum superpositions provides further motivation for examining decoherence channels beyond electromagnetism. Proposals to place mirrors and mechanical oscillators into quantum superposition states [9], together with the development of cavity opto-mechanics as a precision quantum platform [10], highlight the relevance of understanding all potential environmental couplings, including gravity, at increasingly large mass scales. In this paper, we argue that gravitational-wave distinguishability provides a universal information-theoretic channel for decoherence. When alternative quantum histories imprint distinguishable gravitational radiation states into spacetime, coherence is suppressed not by observation, but by the availability of which-branch information in principle. Gravity thus contributes to classicality by functioning as an irreversible which-branch register.

2. Acceleration as the Physical Source of Gravitational Distinguishability

Gravitational radiation (often referred to as gravitational waves), arises from time-dependent mass quadrupole moments; static spatial separations do not generate gravitational waves. In realistic interferometric or guided quantum systems, however, alternative trajectories inevitably involve small differences in their dynamical evolution, including beam steering, curvature, or confinement by external potentials. As a result, the acceleration histories associated with different branches of a quantum superposition are not identical. To quantify this effect, we introduce a path-dependent acceleration contrast defined in Eq. (1):

(1)

$$\Delta a = | a_L - a_R |$$

where a_L and a_R denote the effective accelerations along two alternative trajectories (e.g., the two arms of an interferometer, here labeled “L-left” and “R-right”). These labels do not imply any preferred spatial direction but simply distinguish the two branches of the quantum evolution. The quantity Δa provides a minimal operational measure of dynamical asymmetry between the branches. Since gravitational radiation depends on time-dependent motion, different acceleration histories lead to distinct gravitational field configurations. Consequently, the matter system becomes correlated with branch-dependent gravitational field states, which in principle carry which-path information. To connect this dynamical distinguishability with decoherence, we now translate the acceleration contrast into an information-theoretic measure of coherence loss.

3. Gravitational-Wave State Overlap and Decoherence

To render the distinguishability parameter more explicit, we introduce a phenomenological scaling estimate based on the information carried by the gravitational field. When a system follows different acceleration histories along alternative quantum branches, it imprints branch-dependent signatures in the surrounding gravitational field. These differences encode, in principle, which-path information. From an information-theoretical perspective, decoherence is governed by the distinguishability of the corresponding gravitational field states. Since this distinguishability parameter enters an exponential suppression factor for the interference visibility, it must be dimensionless. A minimal dimensionless scaling ansatz is therefore presented as the parameter $\Delta\Gamma$ which represents the accumulated gravitational distinguishability between the two branches, expressed as a dimensionless measure of their environmental decoherence strength in Eq. (2):

(2)

$$\Delta\Gamma \sim \eta \frac{G m^2 (\Delta a)^2 T^2}{\hbar c^3}$$

where m is the system mass, Δa characterizes the difference between the acceleration histories of the branches, T is the duration over which the trajectories differ, and η is a dimensionless coefficient of order unity that absorbs geometry-dependent and dynamical details not resolved at the present level of description. The appearance of \hbar reflects the fact that distinguishability is fundamentally a quantum measure, governed by phase and information scales set by Planck's constant. The factor c enters as the characteristic propagation speed of gravitational interactions, ensuring that the dynamical contrast between the branches is properly normalized in relativistic terms. The constants G , \hbar , and c together define the natural scale that links gravitational interactions with quantum

coherence. While the combination $G/(\hbar c^3)$ is not dimensionless on its own, it provides—when combined with the relevant dynamical quantities—the unique way to construct a dimensionless measure of distinguishability. Here, c denotes the speed of light in vacuum and sets both the propagation speed of gravitational effects and the natural relativistic scale for comparing dynamical quantities. Eq. (2) captures the expected qualitative behavior of gravitationally induced distinguishability. It vanishes when gravity is turned off ($\mathbf{G} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$), when the two branches undergo identical motion ($\Delta\mathbf{a} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$), or when the duration of branch separation tends to zero ($\mathbf{T} \rightarrow \mathbf{0}$). It also grows with increasing mass and with increasing dynamical contrast between the two trajectories, reflecting the fact that more massive systems and more strongly differing acceleration histories imprint more which-branch information into the gravitational field. Although Eq. (2) is written in terms of the system mass, the gravitational interaction fundamentally couples to energy–momentum rather than rest mass alone. For massless particles such as photons, the relevant scale is therefore set by their energy E , which contributes to spacetime curvature through an effective gravitational mass, E/c^2 . Substituting $m \rightarrow E/c^2$, the distinguishability parameter remains well-defined and non-zero. For typical photon energies, however, the resulting gravitational imprint is exceedingly small, rendering gravitationally induced decoherence negligible in standard optical regimes. To make the scaling more transparent, it is useful to rewrite Eq. (2) in terms of the Planck mass (\mathbf{m}_P) which is written in Eq. (3):

(3)

$$\mathbf{m}_P = \sqrt{\frac{\hbar c}{G}}$$

Using this definition of Eq. (3) in Eq. (2) becomes Eq. (4):

(4)

$$\Delta\Gamma \sim \eta \left(\frac{m}{m_p} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta a T}{c} \right)^2$$

This form makes it explicit that gravitational distinguishability is naturally normalized by the Planck scale. The appearance of m_p does not imply that the system mass itself must approach the Planck mass in order for decoherence effects to arise. Rather, it indicates that the strength of the coupling between quantum coherence and gravitational dynamics is set by the fundamental constants \hbar , c , and G .

Expressed in terms of the accumulated velocity difference $\Delta v \equiv \Delta a T$, the distinguishability parameter takes the form defined in Eq. (5):

(5)

$$\Delta\Gamma \sim \eta \left(\frac{m}{m_p} \right)^2 \left(\frac{\Delta v}{c} \right)^2$$

making clear that decoherence is governed by the kinematic separation between the branches in velocity space. The ratio $\Delta v/c$ provides a relativistically normalized measure of this separation, independent of the specific force or duration that generated it.

Decoherence is expected to become significant when $\Delta\Gamma \sim 1$, corresponding to the regime in which the gravitational field states associated with alternative branches become effectively distinguishable.

The loss of interference may be quantified by the visibility V , which measures the contrast of the interference fringes. In general, visibility is determined by the overlap

between environmental states correlated with the alternative paths of the system.

Denoting these states by $|\psi_1\rangle$ and $|\psi_2\rangle$, as defined in Eq. (6):

(6)

$$V = |\langle \psi_1 | \psi_2 \rangle|$$

The quantity $\langle \psi_1 | \psi_2 \rangle$ is not a classical correlation coefficient but a quantum coherence amplitude: its magnitude determines the survival of interference, while its phase affects only the fringe position. In the present framework, the reduction of this overlap arises from branch-dependent gravitational imprints, summarized by the cumulative distinguishability parameter $\Delta\Gamma$. Assuming $\Delta\Gamma$ results from the accumulation of many statistically independent contributions, the net distinguishability may be modeled by a Gaussian decoherence law. The visibility then takes the heuristic form in Eq. (7):

(7)

$$V \approx \exp\left(-\frac{\Delta\Gamma^2}{2}\right)$$

Equation (7) expresses the suppression of interference as a function of the distinguishability parameter. In particular, the regime $\Delta\Gamma \ll 1$ corresponds to negligible decoherence and near-unit visibility, whereas $\Delta\Gamma \gtrsim 1$ marks the onset of substantial decoherence and loss of interference. This relation provides the quantitative bridge between gravitationally induced distinguishability and experimentally observable coherence.

4. Schrödinger's Cat with Gravitational-Wave Branching

Consider a variant of Schrödinger's cat in which the quantum trigger does not release poison but controls the dynamics of two compact massive objects. In one branch of the

superposition, the objects are released and spiral into each other, forming a black-hole merger and emitting gravitational radiation. In the other branch, the objects remain separated and no gravitational waves are produced.

The global quantum state, $|\Psi\rangle$ may be written schematically as defined in Eq. (8):

(8)

$$|\Psi\rangle = 1/\sqrt{2} (|\text{Cat Alive}\rangle|\text{No GW}\rangle + |\text{Cat Dead}\rangle|\text{GW Emitted}\rangle)$$

Here, $|\text{GW Emitted}\rangle$ denotes a macroscopic gravitational-wave field state corresponding to a black-hole collision, while $|\text{No GW}\rangle$ denotes the gravitational vacuum (or near-vacuum) state. These two gravitational field states are effectively orthogonal. Their overlap is vanishingly small because a black-hole merger imprints an enormous amount of spacetime information into outgoing gravitational radiation. The key point is that no detector is required. Even if no observer ever measures the gravitational waves, the information has already escaped into spacetime. The gravitational field now carries which-branch information in principle. As a result, coherence between the two cat branches is suppressed. The cat is not in a fragile superposition because spacetime itself has become entangled with the alternatives. This thought experiment is not meant as an engineering proposal. It is an idealized limit case designed to isolate the conceptual mechanism: spacetime functions as an irreversible which-branch register.

5. Gravitational-Wave Distinguishability and the Planck-Mass Crossover

At the level of scaling arguments, gravitational distinguishability grows with the mass of the system and with differences in its acceleration history. More massive systems source stronger gravitational fields, and differences in acceleration lead to differences in the emitted gravitational radiation. As a result, alternative quantum histories of a massive

object become increasingly correlated with distinct gravitational-wave field states. Because decoherence is governed by the *distinguishability* of environmental states rather than by energy dissipation, the relevant quantity is not the radiated power, but the amount of which-branch information encoded into the gravitational field. This information grows with the strength of the gravitational coupling and with the duration over which the acceleration histories differ. In quantum terms, any such distinguishability must ultimately be measured relative to Planck constant \hbar , since it reflects the degree to which the gravitational field states associated with different branches become orthogonal in Hilbert space. From a purely dimensional and conceptual standpoint, the Planck mass, m_{P} (see Eq. (3)), is the obvious threshold to test, since it is the only mass built from \hbar (**Planck's constant**), c (**speed of light**), and G (**Newtonian constant**), and therefore marks the point where quantum coherence and gravitational information flow compete on equal footing. The Planck mass emerges as a natural crossover scale. For systems with m (**mass**) $\ll m_{\text{P}}$, the gravitational coupling is so weak that even appreciable differences in acceleration histories fail to imprint significant which-branch information into spacetime. The corresponding gravitational-wave field states overlap strongly, and coherence is effectively preserved. By contrast, when $m \sim m_{\text{P}}$, differences in acceleration histories can render the associated gravitational field states distinguishable in principle. In this regime, spacetime itself begins to function as an efficient which-branch register, and gravitationally induced decoherence becomes unavoidable in an information-theoretic sense. The Planck mass thus does not signal a breakdown of quantum mechanics or the onset of collapse dynamics. Rather, it marks an information-

theoretic boundary between regimes in which gravitational entanglement is negligible and regimes in which it is effectively irreversible.

6. Conceptual Implications

Gravity appears not merely as a background interaction, but as an active information channel. Once gravitational radiation has encoded which-branch information into spacetime, that information cannot be erased by local operations. In this sense, spacetime acts as a memory of quantum histories. This perspective avoids modifying quantum mechanics. Decoherence arises from unitary entanglement with the gravitational field, not from spacetime instability or stochastic collapse. Gravity contributes to classicality by recording information about quantum alternatives in its radiative degrees of freedom.

7. Conclusion

Gravitational radiation provides a natural information-theoretic channel for decoherence in quantum superpositions involving massive systems. When alternative histories generate distinguishable gravitational-wave states, coherence is suppressed not by measurement, but by irreversible information transfer into propagating gravitational degrees of freedom. While both static and radiative gravitational fields encode information, radiative modes uniquely transport which-branch information away from the system, making it effectively inaccessible and thus operationally irreversible. In this framework, decoherence arises when the gravitational field configurations associated with different branches become distinguishable, providing an objective criterion independent of observation. This distinguishability can be quantified by a dimensionless parameter $\Delta\Gamma$, which approaches unity when gravitationally induced decoherence becomes effective. The Planck mass appears as a natural crossover scale that sets the strength of this coupling, rather than as a threshold for dynamical collapse. The Schrödinger's-cat thought experiment, extended to a black-

hole branching scenario, illustrates this mechanism in an extreme limit, where spacetime itself carries persistent which-branch information. This perspective positions gravity not as a modification of quantum mechanics, but as a universal channel through which information loss to inaccessible degrees of freedom contributes to the quantum–classical transition.

Statement on the Use of Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence tools were used only for language editing and stylistic refinement in the preparation of this physics essay. No AI systems contributed to the conceptual development, physical arguments, calculations, or scientific conclusions presented herein. All ideas, derivations, and interpretations are the sole work of the author, who reviewed and verified all AI-assisted text.

References

- [1] W. H. Zurek, 'Decoherence and the transition from quantum to classical', *Physics Today* 44(10), 36–44 (1991).
- [2] W. H. Zurek, 'Decoherence, einselection, and the quantum origins of the classical', *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 75, 715–775 (2003).
- [3] I. Pikovski, M. Zych, F. Costa, Č. Brukner, 'Universal decoherence due to gravitational time dilation', *Nature Physics* 11, 668–672 (2015).
- [4] C. Anastopoulos & B. L. Hu, 'Probing a gravitational cat state', *Class. Quantum Grav.* 32, 165022 (2015).
- [5] M. Blencowe, 'Effective field theory approach to gravitationally induced decoherence', *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 111, 021302 (2013).

- [6] R. Penrose, 'On gravity's role in quantum state reduction', *Gen. Relativ. Gravit.* 28, 581–600 (1996).
- [7] L. Diósi, 'A universal master equation for the gravitational violation of quantum mechanics', *Phys. Lett. A* 120, 377–381 (1987).
- [8] A. Bassi et al., 'Models of wave-function collapse, underlying theories, and experimental tests', *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 85, 471–527 (2013).
- [9] W. Marshall, C. Simon, R. Penrose, D. Bouwmeester, 'Towards quantum superpositions of a mirror', *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 91, 130401 (2003).
- [10] M. Aspelmeyer, T. J. Kippenberg, F. Marquardt, 'Cavity optomechanics', *Rev. Mod. Phys.* 86, 1391–1452 (2014).